

Organometal-catalyzed asymmetric Friedel-Crafts reactions

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Abstract

The Friedel-Crafts alkylation (F-CA) reaction is a distinct sort of Csingle bond C bond formations. It is often used for the formation of Csingle bondC bonds to aromatic rings in organic synthesis. Its enantioselective version frequently provides highly enantiomer as the expected products. Generally, this asymmetric variant of asymmetric Friedel-Craft alkylation (AF-CA) proceeds via an in situ metal catalyzed generation of an enamine as an intermediate. In this report, we are trying to highlight the applications of various optically pure metal catalysts in the

AF-CA as a versatile synthetic strategy in asymmetric synthesis. Metal-catalyzed AF-CA was frequently found as an important and decisive step (steps) for the effective asymmetric synthesis of complex molecules, compounds showing interesting diverse biological activities and especially in the total synthesis of naturally occurring compounds with great and various biological and pharmacological properties.

Keywords: Alkylation, Catalysis, Friedel-Crafts reaction, Asymmetric synthesis, Asymmetric variants, Complex molecules, Friedel-Crafts alkylation